

Terpenoids and Related Compounds-XII¹: Synthesis of Oleana-2, 12-Diene (β -Amyrilene-II)

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Methyl oleanolate (I) has been converted to oleana-2,12-diene (II) through oleana-2,12-diene-28-oic acid methyl ester (III), oleana-2,12-diene-28-ol (IV) and oleana-2,12-diene-28-aldehyde (V).

In a previous communication², we reported the isolation of oleanolic, ursolic and crategolic acids from the flowers of *Eugenia jambolana* Lam. In connection with a scheme for the synthesis of stereoisomeric olean-12-ene-2,3-diols, we required oleana-2, 12-diene, the so-called ' β -amyrilene II'³. Oleanolic acid being available in plenty from the flowers of *E. jambolana*, we attempted to prepare oleana-2,12-diene from it. The present communication describes the successful conversion of methyl oleanolate (I) to oleana-2, 12-diene (II).

Methyl oleanolate² (I) was treated⁴ with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine to furnish oleana-2,12-diene-28-oic acid methyl ester (III), m.p. 180–182° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 180–186°), which on reduction with lithium aluminium hydride gave oleana-2,12-diene-28-ol (IV), m.p. 150–152°, $[\alpha]_D +118^\circ$.

It failed to give a crystalline acetate or a *p*-toluene sulphonate. However, the infra-red spectra of the alcohol (IV) showed a band at 3400 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl).

The diene-alcohol (IV) could not be oxidised satisfactorily by chromium trioxide-pyridine complex⁵, the product being a gummy substance from which isolation of the desired aldehyde by chromatography was difficult. However, oxidation with Jones chromic acid

1. Part XI. P. Sengupta and J. Mukherjee, *Tetrahedron*, in press.
2. *This Journal*, 1965, **42**, 539.
3. J. L. Simonsen and W. C. J. Ross, "The Terpenes", Vol. IV, University Press, Cambridge, 1957, p. 184.
4. R. Tschesche, E. Henckel and G. Snatzke, *Ann.*, 1964, **676**, 175.
5. G. I. Poos, W. F. Johns and L. H. Sarett, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 1026.

reagent⁶ proceeded smoothly and the product after chromatography over silica gel gave in good yield oleana-2,12-diene-28-aldehyde (V), m.p. 164–170°, $[\alpha]_D + 128^\circ$, which showed peaks in the infra-red at 2710 and 1720 cm^{-1} (aldehyde).

The diene aldehyde (V) on Huang-Minlon reduction furnished oleana-2,12-diene (II), m.p. 148–150° (Lit³. m.p. 150–153°). The infra-red spectra showed no bands in the carbonyl and hydroxyl regions, but showed peaks at 820 (trisubstituted ethylene⁷) and 725 cm^{-1} (*cis*-disubstituted ethylene⁷)

EXPERIMENTAL*

Oleana-2,12-diene-28-oic acid methyl ester (III) m.p. 180–182°, $[\alpha]_D + 110^\circ$ was prepared according to the method of Tschesche *et al*⁴ by the treatment of methyl oleanolate (I) with phosphorus oxychloride and pyridine.

Oleana-2,12-diene-28-ol (IV) : The dienoic acid methyl ester (III, 1 g.) was refluxed with lithium aluminium hydride (1 g.) and anhydrous tetrahydrofuran (100 ml) for 8 hr. After cooling, the excess of lithium aluminium hydride was decomposed with crushed ice and the mixture was extracted thoroughly with chloroform. The organic layer was filtered, washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish a crude product (0.9 g.), which was chromatographed over a column of basic alumina (45 g.). Elution with benzene afforded a glass (0.82 g.), which on crystallisation from dil. methanol gave crystals of oleana-2,12-diene-28-ol (IV, 0.65 g.), m.p. 150–152°, $[\alpha]_D + 118^\circ$ (CHCl_3). (Found : C, 85.05; H, 11.51. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}$ requires : C, 84.84; H, 11.39%).

Attempted Acetylation of Oleana-2,12-diene-28-ol (III) : The diene alcohol (0.1 g.) was heated on the water-bath with acetic anhydride (1 ml) and pyridine (1 ml) for 1 hr. and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. Usual working up furnished a glass, which could not be crystallised even after filtration through a column of silica gel (2 g.). A waxy solid, m.p. 60–80° could be obtained on keeping a solution of the product in methanol in a refrigerator for 24 hr. However all attempts at recrystallisation failed.

Attempted Tosylation of Oleana-2,12-diene-28-ol (IV) : A solution of the diene alcohol (IV, 0.1 g.) and *p*-toluene sulphonyl chloride (0.1 g.) in pyridine (1 ml) was allowed to stand at room temperature for 48 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual, when a non-crystallisable glass was obtained.

*Chromic Acid Pyridine Oxidation*⁵ of (IV) : *Oleana-2,12-diene-28-aldehyde* (V) : The diene-alcohol (IV, 0.34 g.) dissolved in pyridine (3.4 ml) was added at 15° to a complex prepared from chromium trioxide (0.34 g.) and pyridine (3.4 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 18 hr. After working up as usual a crude coloured gum (0.34 g.) was obtained, which was chromatographed over alumina (20 g., deactivated with 0.6 ml of 10% aqueous acetic acid). Elution with petroleum afforded a crystalline material (0.08 g.) which on crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and methanol furnished flowery crystals of the diene aldehyde (V, 0.04 g.), m.p. 164–170°, $[\alpha]_D + 128^\circ$ (Found : C, 85.24; H, 10.80. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{46}\text{O}$ requires : C, 85.24; H, 10.97%).

6. K. Bowden, I. M. Heilbron, F. R. H. Jones and B. C. L. Weedon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 39.

7. L. T. Bellamy, "The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1960, p. 48.

* All melting points are uncorrected. The petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

*Jones Oxidation*⁶ of (IV) : *Oleana-2,12-diene-28-aldehyde* (V) : To a solution of the diene alcohol (IV, 0.2 g.) in acetone (8 ml) was added Jones reagent drop by drop through a micro-pipette at room temperature, the mixture being vigorously shaken all the time till the green precipitate no longer formed and the colour of the reagent persisted. After stirring the reaction mixture for further 2 min., cold water was poured into it and the reaction mixture was extracted with CHCl_3 . The organic layer was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish a glassy solid (0.15 g.), which was chromatographed over silica gel (10 g.). Elution with petroleum afforded crystals (0.1 g.), which after crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and methanol furnished the diene aldehyde (V, 0.07 g.), m.p. 164–170°, identical with the above Sarett-oxidation product (mixed m.p.).

Huang-Minlon reduction of (V) : *Oleana-2,12-diene* (II) : The diene aldehyde (V, 0.21 g.), in ethanol (10 ml) and diethylene glycol (40 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 hr. with 80% hydrazine hydrate (3 ml). KOH (0.25 g.) was then added and the mixture refluxed for 1 hr. The condenser was removed and the solution boiled until the inner temperature reached 190°. The condenser was then replaced by a dry one and the solution was heated under reflux for 3 hr. After cooling, water was added to the mixture and the precipitated gum was extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and evaporated to furnish a crude solid (0.2 g.), which was chromatographed over activated alumina (5 g.). Elution with petroleum furnished a solid, m.p. 144–148° (0.16 g.), which on two crystallisations from acetone gave oleana-2,12-diene (II), m.p. 148–150°. (Lit³. m.p. 152–153°). (Found : C, 87.96; H, 11.74. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}$: C, 88.16; H, 11.84%). Positive tetranitromethane test.

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